

POSSIBLE ANTITUBERCULOUS COMPOUNDS. PART V. PREPARATION
OF BENZYLIDENE AND BENZYL DERIVATIVES OF
4'-ACYL-4-AMINODIPHENYLS

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To investigate the effect of basic strength on antitubercular activity, nine substituted N-benzylidene and the corresponding N-benzyl derivatives of 4'-acyl-4-aminodiphenyls have been prepared.

The well known fact that aromatic compounds have to be highly basic for being antitubercular in nature was first noted by Kuroya (*J. Exper. Med. Japan*, 1929, 7, 255). A systematic study of such basic compounds, e.g., 4-aminodiphenyl, naphthylamines and aminobenzothiophenes, which were shown to possess high antitubercular activity, was made by several authors (Bloch, Erlenmeyer *et al.*, *Helv. Chim. Acta*, 1945, 28, 1406; 1947, 30, 1336, 2058, 2063). The other factor which largely contributes to the activity of the synthetic antitubercular compound against *Mycobacterium tubercle* is its high lipid solubility (Adams, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1927, 49, 2934).

The present work has been undertaken to associate lipid solubility with varying basicity in the 4-aminodiphenyl moiety, a known antitubercular compound (*loc. cit.*), thus obtaining structures where the antitubercular activity is augmented by these two factors.

The authors have synthesised a series of substituted N-benzyl derivatives of 4'-acyl-4-aminodiphenyls so as to obtain compounds of basic strength, intermediate between those of primary amines and the N-diphenylamidines, described earlier (Misra and Khare, this *Journal*, 1952, 29, 695; 1953, 30, 45). The acyl group in the molecule is responsible for the lipophilic nature.

The condensation of 4'-acyl-4-aminodiphenyl with aromatic aldehydes afforded the expected benzylidene derivatives in good yields and these were subsequently catalytically reduced with hydrogen in the presence of platinum black at a pressure of 60 lbs. per. sq. inch to the expected benzylamino compounds. The completion of the hydrogenation was confirmed by testing for the free amino group after boiling with concentrated hydrochloric acid, when it was found to be absent. The fact that complete reduction had taken place was also confirmed by finding out the mixed melting points of the two products.

EXPERIMENTAL

4'-Acyl-4-aminodiphenyl was obtained according to the method described earlier (Misra and Khare, *loc. cit.*).

N-Benzylidene Derivatives of 4'-Acyl-4-aminodiphenyl

These derivatives were obtained in quantitative yields by refluxing equimolar quantities of 4'-acyl-4-aminodiphenyl and freshly distilled aldehydes in alcoholic solution for 30 minutes. The crystalline solid which separated out was filtered, after cooling and recrystallised from acetone or dioxane. Their properties are shown in Table I.

TABLE I
Substituted 4'-acyl-4-benzylidene-aminodiphenyls.

Substituent.		M.P.	Yield.	Mol. formula	% Nitrogen.	
X.	Y.				Found.	Calc.
CH ₃	H	193-95°	92%	C ₂₁ H ₁₇ ON	4.81	4.68
CH ₃	<i>ortho</i> -OH	197-99°	96	C ₂₁ H ₁₇ O ₂ N	4.32	4.44
CH ₃	<i>para</i> -OCH ₃	218-21°	95	C ₂₇ H ₁₉ O ₂ N	4.34	4.25
C ₂ H ₅	H	177-79°	98	C ₂₇ H ₁₉ ON	4.63	4.47
C ₂ H ₅	<i>ortho</i> -OH	187-89°	98	C ₂₇ H ₁₉ O ₂ N	4.54	4.25
C ₂ H ₅	<i>para</i> -OCH ₃	192-94°	96	C ₂₃ H ₂₁ O ₂ N	4.48	4.08
C ₃ H ₇	<i>ortho</i> -OH	202°	90	C ₂₃ H ₂₁ O ₂ N	3.91	4.08
C ₃ H ₇	<i>para</i> -OCH ₃	230-32°	96	C ₂₄ H ₂₃ O ₂ N	3.81	3.92
C ₃ H ₇	<i>para</i> -N(CH ₃) ₂	182-84°	86	C ₂₅ H ₂₅ ON ₂	7.08	7.57

N-Benzyl Derivatives of 4'-Acyl-4-aminodiphenyl

The Schiff's bases (0.5 g.), described above, and 30 c.c. of glacial acetic acid were taken in a hydrogenating bottle; 30 mg. of Adams' catalyst was added to it and it was shaken in an atmosphere of hydrogen at a pressure of 60 lbs./sq. inch. for 6 hours. The acid was then neutralised with strong ammonia solution and the solid separated was filtered and recrystallised from alcohol or dioxane. Their properties are shown in Table II.

TABLE II
Substituted 4'-acyl-4-benzylaminodiphenyls.

Substituent.		M.P.	Yield.	Mol. formula.	% Nitrogen.	
X.	Y.				Found.	Calc.
CH ₃	H	148-50°	86%	C ₂₁ H ₁₉ ON	5.00	4.65
CH ₃	<i>ortho</i> -OH	180°	84	C ₂₁ H ₁₉ O ₂ N	4.70	4.41
CH ₃	<i>para</i> -OCH ₃	179-80°	86	C ₂₇ H ₂₁ O ₂ N	4.42	4.23
C ₂ H ₅	H	163-65°	90	C ₂₇ H ₂₁ ON	4.84	4.44
C ₂ H ₅	<i>ortho</i> -OH	179-82°	87	C ₂₇ H ₂₁ O ₂ N	4.62	4.23
C ₂ H ₅	<i>para</i> -OCH ₃	182-84°	86	C ₂₃ H ₂₁ O ₂ N	4.50	4.06
C ₃ H ₇	<i>ortho</i> -OH	160-61°	80	C ₂₃ H ₂₃ O ₂ N	4.12	4.06
C ₃ H ₇	<i>para</i> -OCH ₃	163-65°	82	C ₂₄ H ₂₅ O ₂ N	4.40	3.90
C ₃ H ₇	<i>para</i> -N(CH ₃) ₂	187-89°	92	C ₂₅ H ₂₅ ON ₂	7.15	7.53

The authors are thankful to Dr. A. B. Sen for his kind interest in the work.